

EFFECT OF NISHA- AMALAKI YOGA IN PREDIABETES (PRAMEH POORVAROOPA) – A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Background: Prediabetes is a metabolic condition characterized by impaired glucose regulation and is considered a high-risk state for the development of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. In Ayurveda, this condition can be correlated with *Prameha Poorvaroopa*, which manifests before the full-blown disease of *Prameha*. *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga*, a classical Ayurvedic formulation, is known for its *Pramehaghna*, *Rasayana*, and *Medohara* properties. **Aim:** To evaluate the clinical efficacy of *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga* in patients of prediabetes (*Prameha Poorvaroopa*). **Materials and Methods:** This is a case series involving patients diagnosed with prediabetes based on fasting blood glucose (100–125 mg/dl) and/or HbA1c (5.7–6.4%). Patients were administered *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga* for a specified duration. Clinical symptoms and biochemical parameters were assessed before and after treatment. **Results:** Significant improvement was observed in subjective symptoms like *Prabhuta Mutrata*, *Kshudha-Adhikya*, *Pipasa-Adhikya*, and *Daurbalya*. Objective parameters such as fasting blood sugar and HbA1c showed a favourable reduction. **Conclusion:** *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga* is effective in managing prediabetes (*Prameha Poorvaroopa*) and may prevent progression to overt diabetes when used along with lifestyle modifications.

KEYWORDS: Prediabetes, *Prameha Poorvaroopa*, *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga*, *Ayurveda*, Case Series.

INTRODUCTION

Prediabetes is an intermediate metabolic state between normoglycemia and diabetes mellitus, with a high risk of progression to Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. According to modern medicine, lifestyle modification remains the cornerstone of management; however, long-term compliance is often poor.^[1]

In Ayurveda, *Prameha* is described as a *Santarpanajanya Vyadhi*, “सन्तर्पणोत्था व्याधयः प्रमेहादयः।”, Charaka explains the **etiological factors** of *Prameha* such as: Excessive intake of *Madhura*, *Snigdha*, *Guru Ahara*, *Avyayama* (lack of exercise), *Divaswapna* (day sleep), due to excessive intake of *Kapha*-provoking diet and sedentary habits. All these are classical causes of *Santarpana*, leading to *Kapha* and *Meda* vitiation, leading to *Prameh* symptom's show as *Poorvaroopa* (prodromal features), including excessive urination, turbidity of urine, lethargy, excessive thirst, and fatigue. Early intervention at the stage of *Poorvaroopa* is emphasized to prevent disease progression.^[2]

Nisha-Amalaki Yoga, “निशामलकीयोगः प्रमेहहरः स्मृतः।,” comprising *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*) and *Amalaki* (*Embllica officinalis*), is described in classical texts as beneficial in *Prameha* due to its *Kapha-Pittahara*, *Medohara*, and *Agnideepana* actions.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim: To assess the effect of *Nisha-Amalaki Yoga* in prediabetes (*Prameha Poorvaroopa*).

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate improvement in clinical features of *Prameha Poorvaroopa*.
2. To assess changes in fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels.
3. To observe the safety and tolerability of the formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

Open-label, single-arm case series.

Selection of Patients

Patients attending the OPD were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age between 30–60 years
- Fasting blood glucose: 100–125 mg/dl
- HbA1c: 5.7–6.4%
- Presence of *Prameha Poorvaroopa Lakshana*

Exclusion Criteria

- Diagnosed diabetes mellitus
- Patients on antidiabetic drugs
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Chronic systemic illnesses

Intervention

Drug

Nisha-Amalaki Yoga

Composition

- *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*) – equal part
- *Amalaki* (*Embllica officinalis*) – equal part

Dose and Duration

- 3 g twice daily with lukewarm water Before Food
- Duration: 8 weeks

Pathya-Apathya

Patients were advised *Pathya Ahara*, such as light, low-glycemic foods, and encouraged for regular physical activity.

Assessment Criteria

Subjective Parameters

- *Prabhuta Mutrata*
- *Pipasa Adhikya*
- *Kshudha Adhikya*
- *Daurbalya*

Objective Parameters

- Fasting Blood Sugar
- HbA1c

Assessments were done before treatment and after completion of therapy.

RESULTS

All patients showed notable improvement in subjective symptoms. A reduction in fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels was observed after treatment. No adverse drug reactions were reported during the study period.

DISCUSSION

Nisha-Amalaki Yoga acts by correcting *Agni*, reducing *Kapha* and *Meda*, and improving glucose metabolism. *Haridra* possesses proven hypoglycemic and anti-inflammatory properties, while *Amalaki* acts as a potent antioxidant and *Rasayana*. The formulation effectively addresses the underlying *Samprapti* of *Prameha Poorvaroopa*.

Early intervention at the prodromal stage may halt or delay the progression to *Madhumeha*.

CONCLUSION

Nisha-Amalaki Yoga is safe and effective in the management of prediabetes (*Prameha Poorvaroopa*). It can be considered a preventive therapeutic option in high-risk individuals.

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